

NFDI4Earth Pilot - World Settlement Footprint

VI. Appendix

A: Data List

A-1: WSF Suite

	53,6 GB
WSF2015_cog.tif	17,7 GB
WSF2019_cog.tif	19,3 GB
WSFEvolution_cog.tif	5,7 GB
WSF3D_V02_BuildingArea.tif	3,5 GB
WSF3D_V02_BuildingFraction.tif	1,3 GB
WSF3D_V02_BuildingHeight.tif	2,0 GB
WSF3D_V02_BuildingVolume.tif	4,1 GB

A-2: IÖR Data Suite

IOER_Monitor_Data_Suite	18,862,511,441
<i>\i_1m_footprint_data</i>	
<i>_a_building_footprints</i>	
ids_1m_footprint_buildings_complete_COG.tif	2,626,121,823
ids_1m_footprint_buildings_nonresidential_COG.tif	2,112,539,301
<i>_b_transportation_network_footprints</i>	
ids_1m_transportation_network_footprint_railways_COG.tif	945,653,938
ids_1m_transportation_network_footprint_roads_0_autobahn_COG.tif	854,035,196
ids_1m_transportation_network_footprint_roads_1_bundesstrasse_COG.tif	948,129,545
ids_1m_transportation_network_footprint_roads_2_staatsstrasse_COG.tif	1,088,065,324
ids_1m_transportation_network_footprint_roads_3_kreisstrasse_COG.tif	1,105,777,591
ids_1m_transportation_network_footprint_roads_4_gemeindestrasse_COG.tif	2,050,129,481
ids_1m_transportation_network_footprint_roads_5_hauptwirtschaftsweg_COG.tif	2,022,799,414
ids_1m_transportation_network_footprint_roads_6_sonstigestrasse_COG.tif	2,022,799,414
ids_1m_transportation_network_footprint_roads_7_platz_COG.tif	883,055,246
ids_1m_transportation_network_footprint_roads_8_rollbahn_COG.tif	807,940,254
<i>\ii_10m_surface_coverage</i>	
<i>_a_building_footprints</i>	
ids_10m_surfacecover_buildings_complete_COG.tif	337,775,531
ids_10m_surfacecover_buildings_nonresidential_COG.tif	231,829,955
<i>_b_transportation_network_footprints</i>	
ids_10m_surfacecover_railways_COG.tif	45,406,343
ids_10m_surfacecover_roads_0_autobahn_COG.tif	35,164,723
ids_10m_surfacecover_roads_1_bundesstrasse_COG.tif	45,784,509
ids_10m_surfacecover_roads_2_staatsstrasse_COG.tif	67,564,950
ids_10m_surfacecover_roads_3_kreisstrasse_COG.tif	68,963,699
ids_10m_surfacecover_roads_4_gemeindestrasse_COG.tif	234,480,668
ids_10m_surfacecover_roads_5_hauptwirtschaftsweg_COG.tif	193,426,701
ids_10m_surfacecover_roads_6_sonstigestrasse_COG.tif	39,395,652
ids_10m_surfacecover_roads_7_platz_COG.tif	33,290,404
ids_10m_surfacecover_roads_8_rollbahn_COG.tif	24,910,701
<i>\iii_100m_building_structure</i>	
ids_100m_building_height_median_m_COG.tif	8,730,930
ids_100m_building_volume_m3_COG.tif	27,821,108

A-3: IÖR World Settlement Footprint Reference Dataset

Subject	World Settlement Footprint Reference dataset
Specific subject area	Building and transportation infrastructure footprints Development structure data
Type of data	<p>Raster data</p> <p>Projection: Lambert Azimuthal Equal Area projection (INSPIRE)</p> <p>Footprint data</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Building: general and non-residential > Transportation types * Data type: 1 bit * Value range: [0; 1] * Value unit: none * Ground resolution: 1m <p>Surface coverage data</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Building coverage > Transportation types coverage * Data type: 8 bit integer * Value range: 0.. 100 * Value unit: % * Ground resolution: 10m <p>Development structure data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Building median height * Data type: 16 bit integer * Value range: 0.. 560 * Value unit: m * Ground resolution: 100m > Overall building volume * Data type: 32 bit integer * Value range: 0.. 2,438,660 * Value unit: m³ * Ground resolution: 100m
How the data were acquired	<p>Original data sources: LoD1-DE, GA-DE, ATKIS Basic DLM have been acquired within the framework of the agreement between the IOER and the BKG (Federal Agency for Cartography and Geodesy) for annual data delivery.</p> <p>Data processing was done by Esri products ArcGIS pro and ArcGIS 10.</p>
Data format	Raster data: Cloud optimized GeoTIFF datasets
Description of data collection	Provide a brief description of the conditions that were used for data collection. Describe the factors/samples under study that were used to generate data points and inclusion/exclusion criteria (if necessary). You may also describe how the data were normalized. Max 400 characters (without spaces).

Data source location	Institution: Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development (ROR: https://ror.org/02t26g637) City/Town/Region: Dresden, Saxony Country: Germany Latitude and longitude for collected data: 51°09'51.23" N 10°27'14.83" E (DMS coordinates)
Data accessibility	All datasets will be made available within the IOER Research Data Centre. DOI will be provided Preliminary accessibility via IOER Filr Hosting: https://filr.ioer.de/filr/public-link/file-download/ff808082857c310201864f6fc9227741/1898/-2995676550212494968/IOER_Monitor_Data_Suite.tar File size: 18 GB

Appendix B: EOC Geoservice – Access to Products

WSF 2015 (v2) - [WMS/EOC Downloadservice](#)

WSF 2019 - [WMS/EOC Downloadservice](#)

WSF Evolution - [WMS/EOC Downloadservice](#)

WSF 3D - [WMS/3D-Viewer/EOC Downloadservice](#)

Appendix C: EOC STAC - Requests

Here are listed some sample requests that give an insight about the functionalities and the content of our EOC STAC.

[EOC STAC Landing Page](#)

[Provides API-Capabilities](#)

[List of available Collections](#)

[WSF 2019 – STAC Collection View](#)

[WSF 2019 – STAC Item Search with BBox Germany](#)

[List of STAC items available in the service for Germany \(JSON\)](#)

Appendix D: How to Use EOC EO Products Service STAC with QGIS

1. Install STAC API Browser Extension

2. Create a New Connection by using EOC STAC URL

- Open STAC API Browser
- Click on “new”
- Type in Name (individual) and STAC URL and click “OK”

3. Fetch Collections

- Click “Fetch Collection”
- You can use filter (e.g. by time or geographical extent) to limit your search
- Click “Search” – You get all Items (4.)

4. View Results

- You can select single footprints or add all at once
- By clicking on “View assets” you list all available assets for this item

5. Assets – Add layer

- Click “Select to add as a layer”
- Click “Add assets as layers”

Assets ×

Item WSF2019_v1_10_46
3 available asset(s)

Name	Type	<input type="checkbox"/> Select to add as a layer	<input type="checkbox"/> Select to download
Data	image/tiff; application=geotiff; profile=cloud-optimized	<input type="checkbox"/> Select to add as a layer	<input type="checkbox"/> Select to download
Thumbnail	image/png	<input type="checkbox"/> Select to add as a layer	<input type="checkbox"/> Select to download
Overview	image/png	<input type="checkbox"/> Select to add as a layer	<input type="checkbox"/> Select to download

[Add assets as layers](#) [Download the assets](#)

6. View Dataset

Layer ⊞ ⊗

WSF2019_v1_10_46
Kanal 1: classification (Gray)
0
■ 255

